

Determination of the effects of chitosan from janitor fish (*Pterygoplichthys*) as a de-leading agent for tap water in Cavite, Philippines

Lars Andreille R. Gata*, Mark Kevin M. Camorista, Glenn Michael P. Javier, Mohammed Amin E. Daher, Jed Gian Paul Rosario, Dhan Alexis Sabale, Joel G. Matamis
Medical Laboratory Science Department, School of Health Science Professions, St. Dominic College of Asia, Bacoor, Cavite, Philippines
*Corresponding author: lars.gata@sdca.edu.ph

Abstract

Water is an essential part of life and contributes to humanity's vitality. It is used for drinking, cooking, bathing, washing clothes, cleaning materials and recreation. However, quality of water must be maintained, because tainted water can pose as a health hazard. Besides waterborne microbial and viral agents that contaminate drinking water and harm humans, heavy metals such as lead are just as hazardous to humans as well. The quality of water in Southeast Asian nations has been deteriorating because of rapid population growth, urbanization, and industrialization. The researchers plan to use the tap water from Cavite in the Philippines for the study to determine if chitosan can act as a de-leading agent. This study discussed the average amount of lead found in tap water and if there will be a significant difference on the average amount of lead found in the tap water of Cavite, Philippines, before and after treatment using the chitosan extract from janitor fish (*Pterygoplichthys*). Chitosan is a natural polysaccharide that is found in abundance within the scales of fish. Researchers plan to extract chitosan from the scales of janitor fish (*Pterygoplichthys*), because they are common in the murky waters of the Philippines. Moreover, their species has a high rate of reproducing offspring, and they are inedible. The researchers dried fish scales using sunlight and performed demineralization, deproteinization, and deacetylation to obtain the chitosan extract. Chitosan in a powdered form will be used as a binding agent to attract the lead ions present in the water. The amount of lead in the tap water was measured after the use of chitosan as a de-leading agent using Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometry (AAS) and compared the results of the experimental groups and the control groups through analysis of variance (ANOVA).

Keywords: Chitosan; De-leading; Tapwater; Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometry (AAS); Demineralization; Deproteinization; Deacetylation.

To cite this article:

Gata, L. A. R., Camorista, M. K. M., Javier, G. M. P., Daher, M. A. E., Rosario, J. G. P., Sabale, D. A., & Matamis, J. G. (2021). Determination of the effects of chitosan from janitor fish (*Pterygoplichthys*) as a de-leading agent for tap water in Cavite, Philippines. *SDCA Journal of Medical Technology*, 2, 16-27.

Introduction

Water plays a fundamental role in the health of various organisms. To put it simply, water is the essence of life itself. There are numerous ways to utilize water besides sustaining life. Water can be used for cleaning, washing and recreation. Unfortunately, water can be contaminated and cause adverse effects on one's health (Weinmeyer et al., 2017). It can be a carrier for bacteria, viruses and parasites and as well contains heavy metals such as lead.

Lead is a toxic metal that is obtained from the earth's soil, however, various human activities such as burning fossil fuels, mining and manufacturing. Due to the wide spread of this toxic metal, lead poisoning is one of the most significant environmental health threats, especially for children (Canfield et al., 2003). The most common sources of lead poisoning are paint and old buildings, followed by contaminated soil, air, and water (Mayo Clinic, 2016). Lead poisoning poses a health threat to both urban and rural Filipino communities. Riddell et al. (2007) detailed the elevated blood-lead levels among children living in rural areas of the Philippines caused by various environmental factors. Treatments for lead poisoning is available; however, different steps and parameters can be taken to prevent exposure to lead (Ettinger et al., 2019).

As contaminated water being a source of lead poisoning, the researchers would like to determine a solution for this by conducting a study using the substance, chitosan, as a possible de-leading agent for water. Chitosan is a biopolymer and is a chemically processed form of chitin (Bautista et al., 2017). This biopolymer can be found in most marine animals and fungi. The researchers plan to obtain the chitosan extract from the fish scales of janitor fish (*Pterygoplichthys*). This type of fish can be found in abundance in the swampy and murky waters in the Philippines. Places where janitor fish (*Pterygoplichthys*) can be abundantly found within the Philippines include Prinza water dam in Las Pinas and Laguna De Bay.

Chitosan can be obtained from the shells and scales of most marine animals. The researchers, however, considered the use of other organisms that will not affect the balance of ecosystem and affects the food chain. This idea gave birth to the use of a fish type called janitor fish (*Pterygoplichthys*). This organism was chosen in reference to the research study of Federico et al. (2020) and the article of Fernandez (2016), where it states that janitor fish (*Pterygoplichthys*) is an invasive species that can reduce the fish caught by the fisherfolks and that janitor fish (*Pterygoplichthys*) can cause huge economic losses. Furthermore, it has a thick scale and the researchers deemed to believe that this organism contains chitosan that can be used as a de-leading agent. Janitor fish (*Pterygoplichthys*) is abundant in Laguna de Bay, where the sample was collected.

Objectives of the Study

This study aims to observe the effectivity of chitosan from janitor fish (*Pterygoplichthys*) as a potential agent for de-leading tap water from Cavite, Philippines.

1. To extract the chitosan from the janitor fish (*Pterygoplichthys*).
2. To determine the average amount of lead found in tap water in Imus and Bacoor, Cavite, Philippines.
3. To determine the significant difference on the average amount of lead found in the tap water in Cavite, Philippines before and after treatment.
4. To determine whether the extract of chitosan from janitor fish (*Pterygoplichthys*) is an effective de-leading agent for tap water.

Null Hypothesis

There is no significant difference on the average amount of the lead found in the tap water of Cavite, Philippines, before and after treatment with the chitosan extract from janitor fish (*Pterygoplichthys*).

Research Methodology and Procedures

The research design that was utilized in the study is the experimental type of research for the determination of chitosan from the scales of janitor fish (*Pterygoplichthys*) as a potential agent for de-

leading tap water from Cavite. This experiment will yield a systematic methodology that will guide the researchers to obtain accurate and statistical data needed to discuss the results of the experiment.

Collection of Janitor Fish (*Pterygoplichthys*)

The researchers obtained an adequate amount of janitor fish (*Pterygoplichthys*) that would be enough for three trials. Janitor fish (*Pterygoplichthys*) can be found in abundance in the waters of Laguna De Bay. It is between the Laguna and Rizal provinces. In total, the researchers have obtained 36 janitor fishes (*Pterygoplichthys*)

Transport of Janitor Fish (*Pterygoplichthys*)

After collecting janitor fish (*Pterygoplichthys*) in Laguna De Bay, the researchers stored them in coolers and buckets filled with fresh water. This method will keep the janitor fish (*Pterygoplichthys*) alive and fresh before they are used for their fish scales to extract the chitosan for research. After the collection of janitor fish (*Pterygoplichthys*), the researchers will use the samples to obtain their fish scales to be used as a source for the chitosan extract.

Authentication of Janitor Fish (*Pterygoplichthys*)

As for the authentication of janitor fish (*Pterygoplichthys*), it was done by University of the Philippines in Los Baños. According to UPLB, the sample that the researchers has given them are *Pterygoplichthys disjunctivus*.

Collection of Tap Water

As for the tap water, the researchers collected one liter of water each from five different sites in Bacoor coming from a water treatment facility. As for Imus, samples will be collected from five different sites on Imus with water coming from a deep well. There will be a total of 10 samples of tap water to be subjected to de-leading with the use of the extracted chitosan from janitor fish (*Pterygoplichthys*).

Materials and Methods

After obtaining the fish scales from the eliminated janitor fish (*Pterygoplichthys*), it was washed thoroughly and was then dried under sunlight for 3 days. The dried scales were then grinded and kept in an airtight container. Demineralization is the process which purges minerals from the sample. This method requires the use of 1% HCl solution at room temperature. The ratio of fish scales to volume (mL) of reagent is 1:13. The fish scales were soaked in the 1% HCl for 36 hours. Afterwards, the scales were washed with distilled water to reach a neutral pH and were dried. Deproteinization follows and it will be done by adding 0.5N NaOH solution for 18 hours (1:13). This is where chitin was obtained as an intermediate product. The chitin was thoroughly washed again with distilled water to achieve neutral pH and were dried afterwards.

Furthermore, the chitin was put through the process of decolorizing using two reagents which were potassium permanganate and oxalic acid (1:13). Potassium permanganate was prepared by mixing 1g of KMnO₄ into 100 mL of water. The chitin was soaked in this solution for 1 hour. The use of potassium permanganate is to remove any organic pollutants and leachates that may be attached to the chitin. Moreover, potassium permanganate also has an antimicrobial property and reacts with iron, manganese, sulfur and phenol (Lee, 2001). This was then followed by soaking the chitin in oxalic acid for 1 hour. Oxalic

acid reagent was prepared by mixing 1 g of oxalic acid in 100 mL of water. The use of oxalic acid is for cleaning and washing off the potassium permanganate along with its pollutants (NCBI, 2004). The decolorized chitin product was subjected to washing with distilled water afterwards.

Deacetylation process follows by soaking the chitin product in a beaker filled with 50% NaOH (1:15) (Sivashankari & Prahbaran, 2017). The solution with the chitin product was stirred for 2 hours at 80°C in an oil bath heated by a hotplate. A thermometer was used to monitor the temperature of the heated oil. This process removes the acetyl groups bonded to the chitin to produce the final product which is chitosan. The chitosan product was thoroughly washed with distilled water to achieve a neutral pH. Once chitosan is in a powdered state, it is more consistent in attracting the lead and other heavy metals present in the tap water samples. Once the water has been mixed with the chitosan, it will begin the adsorption process.

Confirmation of Chitosan with FTIR

After obtaining the chitosan extract from the fish scales of janitor fish (*Pterygoplichthys*), the researchers brought their product to the Department of Science and Technology (DOST) in Taguig, Metro Manila. The researchers had their product tested by Fourier-transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR) to confirm whether their chitosan was legitimate or not. The product was confirmed to be chitosan. FTIR spectrometers are instruments that are widely used in organic synthesis, polymer science, petrochemical engineering, pharmaceutical industry and food analysis. In addition to this, FTIR spectrometers could be hyphenated to chromatography, which can help in investigating the mechanism of chemical reactions and the detection of unstable substances (Lin, 2016). The principle behind FTIR is that it measures the intensity of the interference light in an interferogram, with the optical path difference recorded along the horizontal axis (Monnier & Allen, 2013).

Reading with AAS

The researchers recorded the amount of lead using an atomic absorption spectrophotometer (AAS). The specimens that were analyzed will be one with no chitosan mixed in the tap water and the other one will be tap water mixed with chitosan at 1g per 100 mL of tap water as per Al-Manhel et al. (2018). The post-treated water samples will have their lead levels analyzed for 3 trials. Furthermore, the researchers used the AAS from Mach Union Water Laboratory in Las Piñas, Metro Manila. Based on Mao et al. (1997), “*These specimens will be analyzed on the atomic adsorption spectrophotometer with the standardized working conditions were set up as a wavelength of 283.3 nm; low slit of 0.7; pretreatment temperature of 700 °C; atomization temperature of 1700 °C; and read time of 5 seconds.*”

With this knowledge, the researchers will utilize the atomic adsorption spectrophotometer as the basis for whether the experiment has successfully decreased the amount of lead present in the tap water. The spectrophotometer will follow this guideline to have an accurate measurement of the lead concentration. The instrument was furnished with Transverse Heated Graphite Atomizer and Zeeman-Effect Background Correction.

The standardized working conditions were set up as a wavelength of 283.3 nm; low slit of 0.7; pretreatment temperature of 700 °C; atomization temperature of 1700 °C; and read time of 5 seconds. Once these parameters for the spectrophotometer are accomplished, the samples can then be run through and read.

Statistical Analysis

The statistical treatment that is to be adopted for this study is analyses of variance (ANOVA). The researchers will identify the comparable rate of de-lead water from the chitosan extract of Janitor Fish

(*Pterygoplichthys*) versus the positive and negative controls. To put it simply, ANOVA will provide statistical tests of whether the means of several groups were all equal and therefore generalized t-test to more than two groups.

Proper Disposal of Waste

Wastes accumulated from the research were placed in appropriate containers. Biologic and infectious wastes were put in a container labeled with a biohazard symbol and were decontaminated following institutional policy. The waste was used as fertilizer for plants. Additionally, the researchers will disinfect the area and laboratory which will be used for the experiment.

Flow Chart

Figure 1. Flow chart of the procedure

Figure 2. An image showing the scales being submerged in the solution

In Figure 2, after descaling the janitor fish and dried under the sun, the scales were soaked into 1% HCl to remove minerals in the scales.

Figure 3. Filtration of the scales

In Figure 3, after the demineralization step, the samples were filtered and then washed with distilled water to remove the acid from the samples.

Figure 4. Demineralized scales dried under the sun

The sample on Figure 4 shows the scales having been filtered and their pH has been neutralized using distilled water. After filtration the samples were dried under the sun.

Figure 5. Deproteinization of the scales

The sample on Figure 5 shows the deproteinization process accomplished by filtering the samples on the filter paper and washing them using distilled water. After the drying step, the scales were soaked in 0.5 NaOH for the deproteinization process. This is to remove the proteins attached to the scales.

Figure 6. Drying step

Figure 6 shows that the samples were dried and its shows dark pigments. After deproteinization step, the drying step was applied.

Figure 7. (a) Decolorization (b) Neutralization

After drying comes the decolorization phase. Figure 7 shows that this phase was applied to remove any residual minerals, organic dirt, and pigments.

Figure 8. Powdered form of chitin

In Figure 8, after decolorization step, the chitin was obtained, and all the residual elements were removed. The following procedure was to dry the sample.

Figure 9. (a) Deacetylation process (b) Neutralization

In Figure 9, after obtaining pure chitin and drying, the deacetylation step was followed using 50% NaOH.

Figure 10. Powdered chitosan extract from janitor fish (*Pterygoplichthys*)

After the sample was washed, the last step for obtaining chitosan in Figure 10 was drying the product which was the powdered state of chitosan.

Results and Discussion

1. How is the chitosan being extracted from the janitor fish (*Pterygoplichthys*)?

The chitosan was extracted from the janitor fish by way of a four-step procedure, the first of which was demineralization followed by deproteinization, decolorization, and lastly deacetylation.

2. What is the average amount of lead found in the tap water?

Table 1. Lead Content of Sample Water Before Treatment

Sample	Level of Lead
1 (Sample I-A)	<0.006
2 (Sample I-B)	1.309
3 (Sample I-C)	1.08
4 (Sample I-D)	<0.006
5 (Sample I-E)	0.336
6 (Sample B-A)	0.744
7 (Sample B-B)	0.393
8 (Sample B-C)	0.596
9 (Sample B-D)	0.251
10 (Sample B-E)	1.309

Table 1 above shows the result of the water that is untreated with chitosan. It can be gleaned above that all the ten (10) samples collected from various areas in Imus and Bacoor City contain variable amounts of lead. Therefore, it can be concluded that the untreated water level is high from Imus and Bacoor regardless of the source as to whether from water treatment facility or deep well contain lead using Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometry (AAS). Moreover, the result also showed that it is not only in Manila area that it is proven to have tap water found to contain lead based on the study of Solidum et al. (2019), but also in the nearby areas like Bacoor and Imus.

Table 2. Lead Content of Sample Water After Treatment

Sample	Level of Lead		
	Trial 1	Trial 2	Trial 3
1 (Sample I-A)	<0.006	<0.006	<0.006
2 (Sample I-B)	<0.006	<0.006	<0.006
3 (Sample I-C)	<0.006	<0.006	<0.006
4 (Sample I-D)	<0.006	<0.006	<0.006
5 (Sample I-E)	<0.006	<0.006	<0.006
6 (Sample B-A)	<0.006	<0.006	<0.006
7 (Sample B-B)	<0.006	<0.006	<0.006
8 (Sample B-C)	0.0657	0.0654	0.0015
9 (Sample B-D)	0.1539	0.1397	0.1462
10 (Sample B-E)	<0.006	<0.006	<0.006

As gleaned from Table 2, it shows the result when the water sample was treated with the chitosan. It can be observed that the water samples are de-lead as evidenced by the decrease in the level of lead from the samples that are untreated. This result supports the conclusion mentioned by da Silva Mira et al. (2017) that the chelating ability of the chitosan can be used to bind metals like lead.

Table 3. Mean Score of Treated and Untreated Water

Treatment	Mean Score
Untreated	0.528
Treated	0.026

As shown from Table 3, it can be observed that there is difference in the mean score between the samples that are untreated and treated with chitosan. The data revealed that there is a significant decrease in the level of lead on the water samples treated with chitosan from janitor fish. This result proves that chitosan is a natural substance recognized for its property of bio-adhesion, having the ability to absorb heavy metals. Furthermore, it can be concluded that chitosan extracted from janitor fish can have the ability to remove any lead content from water contaminated with it. This also attests that chitosan extracted from fish scales, not only crustaceans, are good de-leading agents.

3. Is there a significant difference in the average amount of lead found in the tap water in Cavite before and after the treatment of using the chitosan extract from janitor fish (*Pterygoplichthys*)?

Table 4. Significant Difference Between Treated and Untreated Samples

Computed p-value	Significance	Ho Decision
0.005	Significant	Reject

Shown in table 4 is the significant difference between water samples untreated and treated with chitosan from janitor fish (*Pterygoplichthys*). The result entails that there is a significant difference on the average amount of lead found in the given samples as evidenced by a p-value of 0.005, therefore null hypothesis is rejected. This result reveals that when the tap water samples are treated with the chitosan extracted from the janitor fish (*Pterygoplichthys*) there is a significant removal of lead proving that it has an ability to absorb heavy metals. Thus, it can be concluded that chitosan from janitor fish (*Pterygoplichthys*) can be an effective de-leading agent as compared to the proven other sources such as crustacean shells.

4. Is the chitosan from janitor fish (*Pterygoplichthys*) an effective de-leading agent for tap water?

Water as an essential part of life survival should be free of any contaminations whether microorganisms or heavy metals. Being said as such, measures should be taken to decontaminate it. In this study, the researchers attempt to remove lead contaminants present from the water samples using chitosan extract from janitor fish (*Pterygoplichthys*). The results show that there is a significant decrease in the level of lead contaminants before and after the treatment. Thus, based on the statements and the results, it can be concluded that janitor fish (*Pterygoplichthys*) can be a de-leading agent for tap water samples obtained from selected areas in the province of Cavite.

Conclusion

From the results obtained from this research, it has been observed, attested and confirmed that chitosan extracted from janitor fish (*Pterygoplichthys*) could significantly de-lead tap water from Imus and Bacoor, Cavite. Furthermore, extraction of chitosan was successful from janitor fish (*Pterygoplichthys*) which is an invasive species in addition to the available, conventional sources chitosan which are crustacean shells such as crabs and shrimps. Lastly, the lead levels in the post-treatment water samples were markedly decreased than the lead levels in the pre-treatment water samples due to the chelating ability of chitosan.

Recommendation

After a thorough analysis of data and its results, the following recommendations are hereby made:

1. For the Local Government Unit, this study may be used to give preventive measures as the basis in constructing guidelines for proper water treatment for the benefit of the community.
2. The study recommended following safety standards in thoroughly treating potable water before ingesting to prevent any possible illness caused by lead poisoning
3. For the community of Cavite, conducting seminars and other types of mass communication as well as safety programs as a necessary tool to promote awareness measures about lead levels in tap water among the community of Cavite as part of its social responsibility drive.
4. For future researchers who wish to study further about this topic, the researcher recommends the use of modern techniques and instrumentation to shorten the time of processing the extraction of chitosan from janitor fish (*Pterygoplichthys*).
5. For future researchers who wish to study further about this issue, it is imperative to look for other beneficial properties of chitosan such as the potential of having antiparasitic attributes and calculating other heavy metals that may be present in tap water such as chromium IV.

References

- Al-Manhel, A. J., Al-Hilphy, A. R. S., & Niamah, A. K. (2018). Extraction of chitosan, characterisation and its use for water purification. *Journal of the Saudi Society of Agricultural Sciences*, 17(2), 186-190. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jssas.2016.04.001>
- Bautista, A. P. R., Sumalapao, D. E. P., & Villarante, N. R. (2017). Synthesis and characterization of epichlorohydrin-crosslinked lumbang (*Aleurites moluccana*)-derived activated carbon chitosan composite as Cr (VI) bioadsorbent. *Annual Research & Review in Biology*, 21(1), 1-7. <https://doi.org/10.9734/ARRB/2017/38259>
- Canfield, R. L., Henderson, C. R., Cory-Slechta, D. A., Cox, C., Jusko, T. A., & Lanphear, B. P. (2003). Intellectual impairment in children with blood lead concentrations below 10 µg per deciliter. *New England Journal of Medicine*, 348(16), 1517-1526. <https://doi.org/10.1056/NEJMoa022848>
- da Silva Mira, P. C., Souza-Flamini, L. E., da Costa Guedes, D. F., & Da Cruz-Filho, A. M. (2017). Evaluation of the chelating effect of chitosan solubilized in different acids. *Journal of Conservative Dentistry and Endodontics*, 20(5), 297-301. https://journals.lww.com/jcde/fulltext/2017/20050/evaluation_of_the_chelating_effect_of_chitosan.4.aspx
- Ettinger, A. S., Leonard, M. L., & Mason, J. (2019). CDC's lead poisoning prevention program: a long-standing responsibility and commitment to protect children from lead exposure. *Journal of Public Health Management and Practice*, 25, S5-S12. <https://doi.org/10.1097/PHH.0000000000000868>
- Federico, E., Verendia, A. D., Vidal, R. J., & Garcia, E. (2020). Potentials of invasive *Pterygoplichthys disjunctivus* (janitor fish) rind as fish skin leather. *LPU-Laguna Journal of Arts and Sciences*, 3(3), 67-73. https://lpulaguna.edu.ph/wp-content/uploads/2022/01/7.-Federico-Verendia-Vidal-Garcia_Janitor-Fish.pdf
- Fernandez, R. (2016, January 16). *Imported 'invasive' species threaten Philippine fishery industry*. The Philippine Star. <https://www.philstar.com/headlines/2016/01/16/1543458/imported-invasive-species-threaten-philippine-fishery-industry>
- Lee, D. G., Ribagorda, M., & Adrio, J. (2001). *Potassium permanganate*. Encyclopedia of Reagents for Organic Synthesis. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9780470842898.rp244.pub2>

- Lin, S. Y. (2016). An overview of advanced hyphenated techniques for simultaneous analysis and characterization of polymeric materials. *Critical Reviews in Solid State and Materials Sciences*, 41(6), 482-530. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10408436.2016.1186598>
- Mao, G. D., Foreback, C. C., & Chu, J. (1997). Measurement of lead in drinking water by atomic absorption spectrometry with Dithizone extraction. *Toxicological & Environmental Chemistry*, 63(1-4), 163-170. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02772249709358526>
- Mayo Clinic. (2016, December 6). *Lead poisoning*. <https://www.mayoclinic.org/diseases-conditions/lead-poisoning/symptoms-causes/syc-20354717>
- Monnier, J. D., & Allen, R. J. (2013). Radio and optical interferometry: Basic observing techniques and data analysis. In T. D. Oswalt & H. E. Bond (Eds.), *Planets, stars and stellar systems* (pp. 325-373). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-007-5618-2_7
- National Center for Biotechnology Information. (2004, September 16). *Oxalic acid*. <https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/compound/Oxalic-Acid>
- Riddell, T. J., Solon, O., Quimbo, S. A., Tan, C. M. C., Butrick, E., & Peabody, J. W. (2007). Elevated blood-lead levels among children living in the rural Philippines. *Bulletin of the World Health Organization*, 85, 674-680. <https://www.scielosp.org/article/bwho/2007.v85n9/674-680/>
- Sivashankari, P. R., & Prabaharan, M. (2017). Deacetylation modification techniques of chitin and chitosan. In J. A. Jennings & J. D. Bumgardner (Eds.), *Chitosan based biomaterials volume 1* (pp. 117-133). Woodhead Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-08-100230-8.00005-4>
- Solidum, J. N., Dahilig, V. R. A., & Omran, A. (2010). Lead levels of water sources in Manila, Philippines. *Annals of Faculty Engineering Hunedoara-International Journal of Engineering*, 8, 111-118. <https://annals.fih.upt.ro/pdf-full/2010/ANNALS-2010-2-18.pdf>
- Weinmeyer, R., Norling, A., Kawarski, M., & Higgins, E. (2017). The Safe Drinking Water Act of 1974 and its role in providing access to safe drinking water in the United States. *AMA Journal of Ethics*, 19(10), 1018-1026. <https://doi.org/10.1001/journalofethics.2017.19.10.hlaw1-1710>